

Havasupai

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Native American (North American) Religions

The Havasupai are a group of Native Americans who have historically inhabited the area now known as the Cataract Canyon of Arizona. They have lived in the Havasupai Reservation since its establishment in 1880. This entry focuses on the Havasupai living in this reservation around the time of 1918. At this time, the Havasupai's primary social and political unit was the family, with no other divisions (such as clans, moieties, or even lineages beyond three generations) acknowledged (Beierle, 2011). Leadership was based upon prestige, and chieftainship is most accurately viewed as the embodiment of this prestige rather than an official leadership role with clearly defined functions (Spier, 1928:235). The Havasupai belief system centered on ideas about the soul and afterlife, spirits and gods, as well as shamanism. "Religion and ceremonialism were not highly developed among the Havasupai and formed only a minor part in tribal life (Beierle, 2011). As a result, the Havasupai religion is only described in limited ethnographic details.

Date Range: 1893 CE - 1921 CE

Region: Havasupai Reservation, 1918

Region tags: North America, United States of America

Havasupai Reservation, Arizona, United States of America, ca. 1918

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research.
- Source 2: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: Cross-cultural codes 4. Ethnology, 11(4), 436-464.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=nt14-001>
- Source 1 Description: Spier, L. (1928). Havasupai Ethnography. Anthropological Papers Of The American Museum Of Natural History. New York City: The Trustees.
- Source 2 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=nt14-000>
- Source 2 Description: Beierle, J. (2011). Culture Summary: Havasupai. New Haven, Conn.: Human Relations

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "Sporadic contacts with European trappers and explorers began around 1776, but acculturation as the result of these contacts was minimal and occurred primarily in terms of items of material culture. In the late nineteenth century further contacts with European-Americans took place as cattle ranchers and mining prospectors encroached on Havasupai land. As a result of these inimical encounters, in 1880 a reservation was established for the Havasupai people in Cataract Canyon. The year 1895 brought about the establishment of a sub-agency and day school on the reservation by the Bureau of Indian Affairs. In the 1940s the loss of territory and natural resources to European-Americans, led to the abandonment by the Havasupai of the annual migration to the plateau for hunting and gathering. By the mid-twentieth century the process of acculturation had rapidly increased as many Havasupai came into individual contact with European-American employers in the course of wage employment, and as the federal government became more involved in tribal affairs" (Beierle, 2011).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification, indicates that the Havasupai were pacified before the 25-year ethnographic present (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification, indicates that the Havasupai were pacified before the 25-year ethnographic present (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Because "religion and ceremonialism were not highly developed among the Havasupai and formed only a minor part in tribal life" (Beierle, 2011), it can be assumed that there was likely not a conception of assigning religious affiliation.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: Because "religion and ceremonialism were not highly developed among the Havasupai and formed only a minor part in tribal life" (Beierle, 2011), it can be assumed that there was likely not a need to actively proselytize and recruit new members.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: The Havasupai do not have an official political office: they have no levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of autonomous bands (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). Further, "...men have become chiefs through inheritance, through prestige and renown, or both. Women are never chiefs. Chieftainship is emphatically not a position; it is the embodiment of certain somewhat vague functions" (Spier, 1928:235). Additionally, "religion and ceremonialism were not highly developed among the Havasupai and formed only a minor part in tribal life" (Beierle, 2011).

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Because "religion and ceremonialism were not highly developed among the Havasupai and formed only a minor part in tribal life" (Beierle, 2011), it can be assumed that there was likely not a conception of apostasy.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 177

Notes: "The Havasupai numbered 177 in 1919" (Spier, 1928:98).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "There are perhaps three types of shaman: those who cure (g̃'íθiỹ'e) weather shamans (possibly called by the same word), and practitioners of a sort (g̃'is'amá) who specialize on fractures, wounds, or snake bites, in following the deer, etc. Apparently all of them dream, but only the first have familiar spirits. These three types are fairly distinct, but not exclusive" (Spier, 1928:277).

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Notes: While there is not a formally institutionalized hierarchy, the curing shaman is regarded as most important (Spier, 1928:278).

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: "Shamanistic power is acquired by inheritance or by dreaming" (Spier, 1928:277).

↳ Powers are inherited:

– Yes

Notes: "Shamanistic power is acquired by inheritance or by dreaming" (Spier, 1928:277).

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– I don't know

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– I don't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: Because "religion and ceremonialism were not highly developed among the Havasupai and formed only a minor part in tribal life" (Beierle, 2011), it can be assumed that scriptures were most likely not present. Additionally, there is no ethnographic evidence for the presence of scriptures.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS variable 66 (Large or Impressive Structures), there are no large or impressive structures among the Havasupai (Murdock and Wilson, 1972; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS variable 66 (Large or Impressive Structures), there are no large or impressive structures among the Havasupai (Murdock and Wilson, 1972; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "Each human has a soul in his heart; the word, yuwai'iv, refers to both soul and heart. It leaves his body at death, but not when he dreams or lies unconscious..." (Spier, 1928:275).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "The souls of dead men are said to go to the north where they live well, but what the hereafter is like and even its location is indefinite in the minds of informants" (Spier, 1928:276).

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Notes: "The souls of dead men are said to go to the north where they live well, but what the hereafter is like and even its location is indefinite in the minds of informants" (Spier, 1928:276).

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of a belief in reincarnation.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "Formerly, the body was placed on a pyre at some distance from the camp, together with the choicest possessions of the deceased. Nowadays it is buried with these objects among the rocks of the lower canyon level somewhere near the falls below the village" (Spier, 1928:292).

Cremation:

– Yes

Notes: "Formerly, the body was placed on a pyre at some distance from the camp, together

with the choicest possessions of the deceased" (Spier, 1928:292).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1800 CE - 1892 CE

↳ **Mummification:**

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mummification.

↳ **Interment:**

– Yes

Notes: "Formerly, the body was placed on a pyre at some distance from the camp, together with the choicest possessions of the deceased. Nowadays it is buried with these objects among the rocks of the lower canyon level somewhere near the falls below the village" (Spier, 1928:292).

↳ **Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):**

– I don't know

↳ **Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):**

– I don't know

↳ **Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):**

– I don't know

↳ **Cannibalism:**

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cannibalism.

↳ **Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):**

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of exposing corpses to the elements.

↳ **Feeding to animals:**

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of feeding corpses to animals.

↳ **Secondary burial:**

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1850, Secondary bone/body treatment; original scale, indicates that "secondary contact with the body or bones of the deceased does not occur" (Schroeder, 2001; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: "Two or three good horses are killed at the grave (their bodies are probably not burned) or they are pushed over the cliff" (Spier, 1928:292).

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of human sacrifices.

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: "Formerly, the body was placed on a pyre at some distance from the camp, together with the choicest possessions of the deceased. Nowadays it is buried with these objects among the rocks of the lower canyon level somewhere near the falls below the village. After a few days such of the dead man's belongings as were in the camps on the plateau are brought down and burned on the grave" (Spier, 1928:292).

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: "...the choicest possessions of the deceased" (Spier, 1928:292) are buried with the body.

↳ Valuable items:

– I don't know

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: For a description of Havasupai burial practices, see Spier, 1928:292-293.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– I don't know

↳ In cemetery:

– I don't know

Notes: It is unclear if bodies are buried in cemeteries/burial grounds.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– I don't know

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– I don't know

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: "...among the rocks of the lower canyon level somewhere near the falls below the village"

Notes: "Formerly, the body was placed on a pyre at some distance from the camp, together with the choicest possessions of the deceased. Nowadays it is buried with these objects among the rocks of the lower canyon level somewhere near the falls below the village" (Spier, 1928:292).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "Religion and ceremonialism were not highly developed among the Havasupai and formed only a minor part in tribal life. As with other Yuman tribes religious beliefs centered around shamanism and magical curing through the use of spirits and dreams. In general the Havasupai believed strongly in the afterlife and ghosts, and dreams to them were a way of making contact with supernatural forces...The Havasupai had few major deities" (Beierle, 2011).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 238 (Note, identical to Ethnographic Atlas Column 34), Religion: high gods, indicates that "a high god is absent or not reported in substantial descriptions of religious beliefs" (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The soul of a dead man may appear as a ghost (ǎmíy~e); this is short and like a shadow" (Spier, 1928:275).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "Shamans alone commonly see ghosts, or rather, their familiar spirits seek them out at night and report their doings, yet others may see them. When a ghost appears to a man it is a portent that a relative will soon die, or else it is to cause the man himself to sicken. Ghosts are said always to be malignant; a man who heard and saw one would sicken that very day and fail fast" (Spier, 1928:275).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Spirits, in distinction to [human] souls, are limited in number. Almost without exception they are shaman's familiars" (Spier, 1928:276). "The character of the spirit is not usually designated, but those specified include a wolf, a hawk, and the spirit of the mythical personage who made the deer" (Spier, 1928:177).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: "Nobody has seen a spirit (s' amáa)" (Spier, 1928:276).

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "Spirits are the cause of illness, although this belief does not preclude that which holds minor ailments due to natural causes, infringements of taboos, or to illy-defined magical practices" (Spier, 1928:277).

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Shaman's familiars live within the chest of the shaman and have a special connection

Notes: "Each shaman has one within his chest. When he wants to discover something he sends the spirit traveling, perhaps for a day and night. The shaman goes out into the darkness; his spirit is heard hollering and whistling to him from a distance. It re-enters his mouth, makes noises, and talks. The shaman shuts his eyes and apparently sings, but in reality it is the spirit telling what it saw" (Spier, 1928:276).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient information

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient information

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient information

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: As with any society, the Havasupai possess general social norms such as life cycle customs, instruction of children, and various taboos. However, "proscribed types of action are not numerous in Havasupai life..." (Spier, 1928:287). For a description of such norms/taboo, see Spier, 1928:287-289.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of fasting.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Notes: "The one general dance (yim`ag`a) of the year is hardly to be classed as religious, for it serves a social end, yet it is also a means of obtaining rain and prosperity. Certainly the pleasure element is uppermost for the majority of those attending. It is performed at the end of August or the beginning of September, when the harvest is gathered" (Spier, 1928:261).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A band

Notes: The Havasupai have no levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of autonomous bands (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). "There are six chiefs today, one of whom occupies a superior status and is recognized by the agent as the head chief; the others are equally leaders. These men have become chiefs through inheritance, through prestige and renown, or both. Women are never chiefs. Chieftainship is emphatically not a position; it is the embodiment of certain somewhat vague functions" (Spier, 1928:235).

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: The Havasupai have no levels of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is indicative of autonomous bands (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, indicates that food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: It can be assumed that transportation infrastructure is not present, as routes of land transport are "unimproved trails", according to Murdock and Morrow (1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004; SCCS Variable 14).

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: "Police functions are not specialized or institutionalized at any level of political integration, the maintenance of law and order being left exclusively to informal mechanisms of social control, to private retaliation, or to sorcery" (Tuden and Marshall, 1972, Column 10).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: "It is not clear that there is any other function beside giving advice...It is quite clear that chiefs have neither power nor prerogatives; they are simply leaders" (Spier, 1928:236).

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: "It is not clear that there is any other function beside giving advice...It is quite clear that chiefs have neither power nor prerogatives; they are simply leaders" (Spier, 1928:236).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Havasupai relied primarily on intensive agriculture supplemented by hunting and gathering. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004;

Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: "Traditionally the Havasupai were agriculturalists, with the growing of maize, beans, squash, and melons in irrigated fields. This was supplemented by the gathering of fruits, berries and other wild foods by the women, and the hunting of rabbits, antelope, deer, and mountain sheep by men. Trade with neighboring tribes was also important to the economy" (Beierle, 2011).